

Studies in Copper(II) Chelates: Part VI. 5-Nitro-*o*-Phenanthroline Mono(Biguanide)Copper(II) Complexes

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Whereas syntheses of complexes, κ, κ' -dipyridyl mono(methyl/ethylbiguanide)copper(II) could be achieved¹ the same methods failed to provide the corresponding *o*-phenanthroline complexes. This, we conjectured was due to (1) the very small *pH* range where the mono(alkylbiguanide)copper(II) —bis(alkylbiguanide)copper(II) equilibrium existed, (2) high stability of the mono(*o*-phenanthroline)copper(II) complex compared to that of the mixed chelate and (3) the lower solubility of the mono (*o*-phenanthroline) copper (II) complex compared to the corresponding κ, κ' -dipyridyl compound.

We therefore looked for some *o*-phenanthroline derivative where the sought-for synthesis would not be vitiated. It was finally possible to prepare a series of mixed chelates of copper (II) having 5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline and a biguanide, N¹-methylbiguanide or an N¹-ethylbiguanide. The most important factor governing the syntheses of the mixed chelates was the *pH* of the solution containing the biguanide or substituted biguanide in order to keep the Cu²⁺ in solution as the bis (complex) and then the 5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline was added around *pH* 7. It is pertinent to mention that even on setting these same conditions, we failed to isolate any mixed copper (II) chelate with *o*-phenanthroline and N¹-methylbiguanide or N¹-ethylbiguanide. The chloride and the bromide salts have been obtained in pure state as sky-blue coloured material. All attempts to isolate the iodide salt have failed. Addition of thiocyanate, azide or nitrite ion to an aqueous solution of the mixed-complex chloride provided merely the precipitates of the highly insoluble diisothiocyanato-, diazido- or dinitromono(5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline)-copper(II) complexes (cf. Part I of this series)¹.

The aqueous solution absorption spectra reveal for all the complexes a somewhat broad and asymmetric peak and compares well with the *o*-phenanthroline mono(biguanide)-copper (II) system. Compared to the square planar bis(biguanide)copper(II) the spectra shifts considerably to lower frequency. Spectra run in several solvents of varying donor properties (water, ethyleneglycol and dimethylsulfoxide) seem to be solvent dependent (cf. Fig. 1 and Table 1). Prominent shoulders also appear in the DMSO spectra of 5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline mono(methylbiguanide)copper(II) and 5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline mono(ethylbiguanide)copper(II) chloride. Distorted octahedral structure is proposed for the chelates at least in solution²⁻⁵.

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Fig. 1. Solution Absorption Spectra of 5-Nitro-*o*-phenanthroline mono(biguanide) mixed chelates in different solvents at 0.004M.

- (1) [Cu (nitrophen) (EtBigH)] Cl₂.H₂O, in aqueous medium.
- (2) [Cu (nitrophen) (MeBigH)] Cl₂.0. 5H₂O, in aqueous medium.
- (3) [Cu (nitrophen) (BigH)] Cl₂.0. 5H₂O, in aqueous medium.
- (4) [Cu (nitrophen) (MeBigH)] Cl₂.0. 5H₂O, in DMSO.
- (5) [Cu (nitrophen) (MeBigH)] Cl₂.0. 5H₂O, in ethyleneglycol.
- (6) [Cu (nitrophen) (EtBigH)] Cl₂.H₂O, in DMSO.
- (7) [Cu (BigH)₂] Cl₂. 2H₂O, in aqueous medium.

TABLE I

Absorption Spectral Data of the Mixed Chelates

Complex	State	Colour	Absorption Spectral Band (cm ⁻¹)	ε _{max}
1. [Cu (BigH) ₂]Cl ₂	Aq. Soln.	Rose-red	19,230-18,870	41.25**
2. [Cu (nitrophen) (BigH)] Cl ₂	Aq. Soln.	Deep sky-blue	16,670-15,620	51.65
	DMSO	Light green	14,290-13,330	69.00
	Ethyleneglycol	Deep sky-blue	16,130-14,930	62.00
3. [Cu (nitrophen) (MeBigH)] Cl ₂	Aq. Soln.	Deep sky-blue	16,390-15,380	58.75
	DMSO	Yellowish green	(i) 13,890-13,160	63.00
	Ethyleneglycol	Light sky-blue	(ii) 20,830-20,410(sh)	43.50
4. [Cu (nitrophen) (EtBigH)]Cl ₂	Aq. Soln.	Deep sky-blue	16,390-15,380	69.00
	DMSO	Yellowish green	(i) 13,890-13,160	63.00
	Ethyleneglycol	Light sky-blue	(ii) 20,410-20,000(sh)	45.00
5. [Cu(nitrophen) (BigH)]Cl ₂	[Cu(BigH) ₂] Cl ₂ in aq. soln. and nitrophen in 1:1 ratio at pH 7 in aq.-alc. soln.	Deep sky-blue	16,670-15,380	62.50*
	[Cu (MeBigH) ₂] Cl ₂ in aq. soln. and nitrophen in 1:1 ratio at pH 7 in aq. -alc. soln.	Deep sky-blue	16,670-15,380	58.75

TABLE I (contd.)

Complex	State	Colour	Absorption Spectral Band (cm ⁻¹)	ϵ_{\max}
7. [Cu (nitrophen) (EtBigH)] Cl ₂	[Cu (EtBigH) ₂] Cl ₂ in aq. soln. and nitrophen in 1:1 ratio at pH 7 in aq. alc. soln.	Deep sky-blue	16,670-15,620	67.50

*Some variations in molar extinction co-efficients of the complexes are inevitably observed in changing the solvent from 100% water to 1:1 aqueous-alcohol.

**Extinction co-efficient value reported by Ray and Rây⁸ is 38.50 (at 19, 230 cm⁻¹).

sh=shoulder; DMSO=dimethylsulfoxide.

The magnetic moments of all the complexes are around 1.80 B.M. Most copper (II) compounds have moments in the range 1.7-2.1 B.M. The tetrahedral range is 2.0-2.2 B.M. and planar range is ~1.73 B.M.^{6,7} All these complexes provide conductance in aqueous medium as expected for bi-univalent electrolytes (cf. Table II).

TABLE II

Conductance and Magnetic Moments of Mixed Chelates

Complex	Λ_M (at t°C) mohs cm ² mole ⁻¹	Dia. Corr. × 10 ⁶	$\chi_M(\text{corr.})$ × 10 ⁶	$\mu_{\text{eff.}}$ (at T°abs.) B.M.
1. [Cu (nitrophen) (BigH)] Cl ₂ .0.5H ₂ O	229.7 (24°C)*	212	1428	1.85 B.M. (297°abs.)*
2. [Cu (nitrophen) (MeBigH)] Cl ₂ . 0.5H ₂ O	202.7 (23°C)	230	1349	1.82 (307° abs.)
3. [Cu (nitrophen) (EtBigH)] Cl ₂ H ₂ O	216.0 (23.5°C)	249	1363	1.83 (305 abs.)

Λ_M (Molar Conductance) = 2 χ mean $\lambda \propto$, where $\lambda \propto = \lambda v (1 + 0.692 \times n_1 \times n_2 \times v^{-\frac{1}{2}})$ and n_1 and n_2 are the valencies of the ions.

$\mu_{\text{eff.}} = 2.84 (\chi_M(\text{corr.}) \chi T)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ B.M., where T=absolute temp.

*Figures in parentheses indicate temps. (°C. or absolute) at which measurements were made.

BigH=Biguanide, MeBigH=Methylbiguanide, EtBigH=Ethylbiguanide, nitrophen=5-Nitro-*o*-phenanthroline.

Extensive spectrophotometric measurements in aqueous solution have been completed on the formation and composition of all these mixed chelate systems. These solution studies have confirmed the formation of 1:1 mixed chelates. The optimum pH range of formation and stability of the complexes have been evaluated as also the formation constants, following the same techniques and assumptions as in Part I of this series. The formation constant values (10⁸-10⁹) compare favourably with the values obtained for the α, α' -dipyridyl/*o*-phenanthroline mono(biguanide) system (cf. Table-III).

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TABLE III

Formation Constant Values of the Heterochelate Complexes

Initial concn. of bis (biguanide or subst. biguanide) complex=0.004M.

Initial concn. of 5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline (nitrophen)=0.004M.Wavelength of measurements=620 m μ . ϵ [Cu (nitrophen) (BigH)] Cl₂=62.50 ϵ [Cu (nitrophen) (EtBigH)] Cl₂=67.50 ϵ [Cu (nitrophen (MeBigH)]Cl₂=58.75 ϵ [Cu (nitrophen)]²⁺=11.50

System	pH of measurements	O. D. (1-cm cell)	Concn. of [Cu(nitrophen)] ²⁺ × 10 ³	[Mixed complex] × 10 ³	[BigH] or [Subst. BigH]	K
1. [Cu (BigH) ₂] Cl ₂ and nitrophen	4.5	0.173	1.510M	2.490M	5.510 × 10 ⁻¹⁰ M	2.99 × 10 ⁹
	5.0	0.210	0.784	3.215	1.437 × 10 ⁻⁹	2.85 × 10 ⁹
2. [Cu (MeBigH) ₂] Cl ₂ and nitrophen	4.5	0.115	2.540	1.460	7.298 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	7.87 × 10 ⁸
	5.0	0.160	1.588	2.412	2.032 × 10 ⁻⁹	7.48 × 10 ⁸
3. [Cu (EtBigH) ₂]Cl ₂ and nitrophen	4.5	0.108	2.893	1.107	7.120 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	5.37 × 10 ⁸
	5.5	0.212	1.035	2.965	5.380 × 10 ⁻⁹	5.32 × 10 ⁸

EXPERIMENTAL

1. *5-Nitro-*o*-phenanthroline mono(biguanide)copper(II) chloride*: Biguanide acid sulfate (0.9 g.) dissolved in hot water (10 ml) was treated with an aqueous solution of barium chloride (1.2 g in 5ml.). The mixture was digested on a steam-bath and was filtered. An aqueous solution of copper (II) chloride (0.34 g in 2 ml) was added to the filtrate and the pH raised to 7.0 by 2N NH₄OH giving a red-violet colour. An alcoholic solution of 5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline (0.23 g in 5 ml) was added resulting in a sky-blue solution. Immediately bright, sky-blue coloured crystals started crystallising out. These were further recrystallised from warm water, finally washed with alcohol and dried in air.

(Found : Cu, 13.51 ; N, 23.83; Cl, 15.08; H₂O, 2.10 [Cu (nitrophen) (BigH)]Cl₂ · 0.5H₂O requires Cu, 13.56; N, 23.88; Cl, 15.13; H₂O, 1.92%).

2. *5-Nitro-*o*-phenanthroline mono (biguanide) copper (II) bromide*: The above chloride was dissolved in minimum volume of warm water and was treated with a dilute solution of KBr. The light sky-blue crystals were further purified from warm water, finally washed with ethanol and dried in air.

(Found: Cu, 11.53; N, 20.44; Br, 29.22. [Cu (nitrophen) (BigH)] Br₂ requires Cu, 11.58; N, 20.40; Br, 29.17%).

3. *5-Nitro-*o*-phenanthroline mono (methylbiguanide) copper (II) chloride* This was prepared like the above chloride salt at pH 7-7.5 and by allowing the solution to stand for several hours.

(Found : Cu 13.12; N, 23.20; Cl, 14.75; H₂O, 1.90. [Cu (nitrophen) (MeBigH)] Cl₂ · 0.5H₂O requires Cu, 13.17; N, 23.18; Cl, 14.71; H₂O, 1.86%).

4. *5-Nitro-*o*-phenanthroline mono(methylbiguanide)copper(II) bromide*: It was prepared like the above bromide salt.

(Found : Cu, 12.90; N, 18.18; Br, 25.92; H₂O, 8.68. [Cu (nitrophen) (MeBigH)] Br₂ · 3H₂O requires Cu, 12.95; N, 18.13; Br, 25.89; H₂O, 8.73%).

5. *5-Nitro-o-phenanthroline mono(ethylbiguanide)copper(II) chloride*: Procedure similar to no. 1 was followed and the solution allowed to stand for 24 hrs. and finally recrystallised from warm water. (Found : Cu, 12.52 ; N, 22.15; Cl, 14.10; H₂O, 3.61. [Cu (nitrophen) (EtBigH)]Cl₂.H₂O requires Cu, 12.54; N, 22.11; Cl, 14.02; H₂O, 3.55%).

Bis(biguanide/substituted biguanide)copper(II) chloride salts were synthesized by following published procedures.

Analytical Methods : The complexes were fused with KHSO₄, heated with conc. H₂SO₄ to dense white fumes, extracted with dilute H₂SO₄ and copper finally estimated iodometrically. Nitrogen was determined by combustion and halides as silver halides. Hydration content was estimated by loss at 110-120°.

Conductance and magnetic measurements were done as described previously.

Spectral Studies : Solution spectral studies on the composition and formation pH range were run at 0.004M bis (biguanide/subst. biguanide)-copper(II) chloride level. The weighed 5-nitro-o-phenanthroline was dissolved in about 10 ml hot rectified spirit, then weighed amount of the complex dissolved in ~8 ml water was added.

The other experimental procedures and spectral studies were carried out as described in Part 1'.

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